

Impact of Community Watch Corps for Community Safety on Banditry Activities in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examines impact of community watch Corps for community safety on Banditry activities in Katsina State. The study was guided by four research objectives and corresponding research questions. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Population of the study comprised of residents of 10 frontline local government areas in Katsina State. Sample for the study consisted of 100 residents in Jibia and Batsari drawn using a multistage sampling technique. Data for the study were collected using a 20 items questionnaire entitled the Effectiveness of Community Watch Corps in Combating Banditry (ECWCCB). The Instrument was validated by three experts in terms of face, content and construct validities. It was also, pilot tested and obtained a reliability index of 0.086 using PPMC. Descriptive statistics was used in analyzing the collected data. Research questions were analyzed using Mean, and Standard deviation. Findings among others revealed that the strategies employed by community-led groups to enhance local security, fosters collaboration with law enforcement agency, and build community resilience against crime. Based on the findings, the study concluded that Community Watch Corps are active and effective in combating banditry activities in Katsina state. It was further recommended that empowering community watch initiatives can significantly contribute to reducing crime rates and enhancing community safety especially in vulnerable areas.

Keywords: Role, Community Watch Corps, Combating Banditry

Introduction

Katsina State governor, Dikko Radda, on Tuesday 11 October, 2023, inaugurated the Community Watch Corps to complement efforts of conventional security agencies in the fight against banditry in the state (Babangida, 2023). While inaugurating the Batch 1 of the Corps, Mr Radda said it was part of his administration's efforts to adopt a "community-driven" approach towards addressing insecurity in the state. According to Babangida (2023) the statement by the governor's spokesperson, Ibrahim Kaula, the first batch of the Corps consists of 2,400 youths selected from across the 34 local government areas of the state. "The very essence of this corps lies in community engagement, collaboration, and mutual respect. By leveraging localised knowledge and fostering trust, we are not merely addressing symptoms but targeting the roots of insecurity in our state," the statement quoted Mr. Radda as saying (Babangida, 2023).

In recent years, Katsina State has faced escalating challenges from banditry, threatening the safety and security of its communities. Traditional law enforcement methods have struggled to address the pervasive nature of these criminal activities, prompting the need for innovative local solutions. The establishment of Community Watch Corps represents a grassroots response aimed at restoring safety and trust within affected areas. By harnessing local knowledge and fostering community solidarity, these volunteer groups play a crucial role in identifying threats, sharing information, and deterring criminal activities. This paper explores the effectiveness of the Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State, highlighting their strategies, successes, and the importance of

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community involvement in the broader fight against insecurity. The rise of banditry in Nigeria, particularly in Katsina State, has prompted various strategies to enhance community safety. Among these, the establishment of Community Watch Corps (CWC) has emerged as a critical local response. This literature review explores the role of CWC in addressing banditry, focusing on community engagement, effectiveness, and challenges faced.

Community Engagement in Crime Prevention in Katsina state

Community policing has been recognized as an effective strategy in crime prevention. According to Goldstein (1990), community-oriented policing fosters collaboration between law enforcement and communities, enhancing trust and cooperation. The CWC in Katsina aligns with this model, empowering local citizens to take an active role in their security. Studies show that community involvement increases the likelihood of reporting suspicious activities, which is crucial in a region plagued by banditry (Omoera, 2017).

Effectiveness of Community Watch Corps in Katsina state

Research indicates that CWC initiatives have led to significant reductions in crime rates in some Nigerian communities. For instance, a study by Adebayo and Olaoluwa (2020) demonstrated that community watch groups in the northern regions effectively deterred criminal activities by increasing surveillance and community vigilance. In Katsina, the CWC has adopted similar strategies, forming alliances with local law enforcement to enhance their capacity to respond to banditry (Umar & Bello, 2021).

Challenges Faced by Community Watch Corps in Katsina State

Despite the successes, several challenges hinder the effectiveness of the CWC in Katsina State. A major issue is the lack of training and resources, which limits the operational capacity of community watch members (Ismail & Yahaya, 2019). Additionally, tensions between community watch groups and formal law enforcement agencies can lead to conflicts, undermining collaborative efforts (Afolabi, 2021). Furthermore, the stigma associated with vigilante groups can deter community members from participating, limiting the CWC's reach and effectiveness (Mohammed, 2022).

The Community Watch Corps plays a vital role in combating banditry in Katsina State through enhanced community engagement and collaboration with law enforcement. While promising, the CWC faces significant challenges that must be addressed to improve its effectiveness. Future research should focus on strategies to strengthen the capacity of these community groups and foster better relations with formal security agencies.

Banditry has become a pervasive security threat in northern Nigeria, particularly in Katsina State. Over recent years, communities in Katsina have been terrorized by armed bandits, leading to the loss of lives, displacement, and destruction of property (Audu, 2021). In response, the state government, in collaboration with local communities, has initiated various security measures, including the establishment of Community Watch Corps. This literature review explores the role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State, emphasizing their effectiveness and challenges.

Concept of Community Policing and Watch Corps

Community policing refers to a strategy that emphasizes the partnership between law enforcement agencies and community members in ensuring public safety (Davis & Henderson, 2003). It is a people-centered approach that involves citizens in crime prevention and control. Community Watch Corps, in particular, are informal security outfits made up of local volunteers who assist formal security agencies in maintaining peace and order (Usman & Musa, 2022).

According to Usman and Musa (2022), Community Watch Corps typically function in rural settings where formal policing is limited. Their intimate knowledge of the local terrain, culture, and people gives them an advantage in identifying criminal elements and preventing crimes like banditry. Furthermore, they act as mediators and provide intelligence to government security forces, often leading to arrests and disruptions of criminal networks.

Banditry activities in Katsina State

Banditry in Katsina State is part of the broader security crisis in the northwestern region of Nigeria. It involves various forms of criminal activities, including cattle rustling, kidnapping for ransom, armed robbery, and murder (Audu, 2021). The porous borders between Nigeria and neighboring countries have exacerbated the problem, facilitating the movement of arms and criminal elements. The rural areas, where security infrastructure is weak, are particularly vulnerable to attacks (Ibrahim & Abubakar, 2020).

Ibrahim and Abubakar (2020) emphasize that the failure of conventional security agencies to curb banditry in Katsina State has led to the formation of community-led security initiatives such as Community Watch Corps. The state government's involvement in these initiatives has added a layer of coordination between the local volunteers and formal law enforcement, enhancing the effectiveness of both groups.

The Role of Community Watch Corps in Combating Banditry activities in Katsina State

Community Watch Corps in Katsina State have played significant roles in combating banditry by providing real-time intelligence to security agencies, conducting patrols, and serving as a deterrent to criminal activities. According to Mohammed (2021), their role has been particularly critical in remote areas where the presence of law enforcement is minimal. One of the key contributions of the Community Watch Corps is intelligence gathering. Mohammed (2021) notes that local volunteers are often more trusted by the rural populace than formal security agencies. As a result, they can gather crucial information about the movements and plans of bandit groups, which they relay to government forces for timely intervention. In addition to intelligence gathering, the Community Watch Corps also participate in joint patrols with the police and military (Audu, 2021). These joint efforts have led to the reduction of bandit attacks in some local government areas. For example, Audu (2021) cites the success of such patrols in Batsari and Jibia, where coordinated operations between the Watch Corps and the military resulted in the arrest of several bandit leaders.

Challenges Facing Community Watch Corps in Katsina State

Despite their contributions, the Community Watch Corps face significant challenges that hinder their effectiveness. One major issue is the lack of proper training and equipment (Usman & Musa, 2022). Unlike formal security agencies, the Watch Corps are often poorly funded, and their members are not trained in modern security tactics. This leaves them vulnerable to attacks by better-armed bandits, reducing their capacity to respond effectively. Another challenge is the legal status of the Community Watch Corps. Since they operate informally, there is often a lack of clarity about their authority, which can lead to conflicts with formal law enforcement agencies (Mohammed, 2021). Without legal recognition, they may also struggle to access funding and other resources needed to carry out their activities effectively. Additionally, issues of mistrust and corruption can affect their operations. Ibrahim and Abubakar (2020) point out that in some cases, community members may be reluctant to provide information to the Watch Corps due to fears of collusion with bandits or retaliation.

The role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State is crucial in bridging the gap between formal security agencies and rural communities. Their involvement in intelligence gathering, joint patrols, and crime prevention has contributed to the reduction of banditry in some areas. However, challenges such as inadequate training, poor equipment, and legal ambiguity continue to limit their overall effectiveness. To maximize their potential, there is a need for better coordination, capacity building, and legal recognition of their operations.

The dismal increase of the number of internally displaced persons (IDPs) from rural to urban centres for asylum have become a source of concern to security stakeholders and government of Katsina State (Babangida, 2023). In spite of the huge amount of money budgeted for procuring ammunition and allowances to security operatives in order to restore peace and harmony in Katsina State, which proved abortive (Babangida, 2023). There is no known study to the best knowledge of the researcher carried out to examine the role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State, Nigeria. The paucity of empirical evidences in this regard necessitates the need to investigate if the Community Watch Corps are well armed can mitigate the menace of banditry acts in Katsina State and other states in Northeast Nigeria.

Research Objectives

This study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To assess the effectiveness of Community Watch Corps activities in reducing banditry incidents in Katsina State.
2. To analyze the collaboration between Community Watch Corps activities and law enforcement agencies in combating banditry.
3. To evaluate community perceptions of Community Watch Corps' role in enhancing security.
4. To identify challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities against banditry.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does Community Watch Corps reduces the incidence of banditry in Katsina State?
2. What is the nature of collaboration between the Community Watch Corps activities and law enforcement agencies?
3. What is the level of perception among community members on the role of Community Watch Corps activities in maintaining security?
4. What are the challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities in their efforts to combat banditry?

Methodology

The research adopted a descriptive survey research designs. The choice of this particular research design was justified because the data used for this study was obtained from the residents bedeviled by perennial insecurity. The population for this study comprised of all the ten (10) frontline Local Governments areas in Katsina state. Population of the study are: Batsari, Danmusa, Jibia, Kankara, Safana, Faskari, Sabuwa, Funtua, Dutsinma and Dandume. Sample for the study consisted of 100 residents in Jibia and Batsari. The sample for the study was collected using a Multistage Sampling Technique. The first stage will involve the purposive selection of two Local Government areas based on proximity to the researcher. Stage Two involved the use of simple random sampling technique to select the sample from the selected Local Government areas.

Data Collection and Analysis

The collected data were subjected to analysis using descriptive statistics of frequencies, mean and standard deviation with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). However, The Instrument was designed and coded on four Likert rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) to illicit information from the respondents on role of community watch corps in combating banditry in Katsina state, Nigeria. The codes were sums up as $4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 10 / 4 = 2.50$ as the cut off criteria for rejection or acceptance of the mean rating, in which mean scores of equal to or greater than 2.50 are accepted and also rejected when it is less.

Presentation of Results

The purpose of this study is to analyze role of Community Watch Corps in combating banditry in Katsina State. Below is the analysis:

Research Question One: To what extent does Community Watch Corps reduces the incidence of banditry in Katsina State?

Table 5: Community Watch Corps efforts to reduce the incidence of banditry

S/N	Statements	M	SD	Decision
1.	Community Watch Corps are quite gallant in their operations by providing the support to security agencies against banditry	2.53	1.18	Accepted
2.	Community Watch Corps enjoyed great acclaim and commendation from the security agencies for their commitment and courage in the war against banditry	2.69	1.11	Accepted
3.	The Community Watch Corps operatives are mandated to kill any culprit caught over alleged involvement in sharing information with the bandits	2.86	1.05	Accepted
4.	Most of Community Watch Corps were vigilante and have passion to protect their communities	2.91	1.04	Accepted
5.	The Community Watch Corps are up to the task of restoration of peace and harmony in Katsina State	2.69	1.09	Accepted
		2.74	1.09	

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 5 revealed that the mean rating ranges from M = 2.50, SD = 1.18 to M = 2.91, SD = 1.04 with overall mean of M = 2.74, SD = 1.09 that is $< M = 2.53$ and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents have accepted that the Community Watch Corps assisted in combating the incidence of banditry in Katsina State.

Research Question Two: What is the nature of collaboration between the Community Watch Corps activities and law enforcement agencies?

Table 6: Nature of the collaboration between the Community Watch Corps and law enforcement agencies

S/N	Statements	M	SD	Decision
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6.	The Community Watch Corps in my community collaborate with other security agencies in minimizing crimes	2.73	1.07	Accepted
7.	Setting up of joint taskforce with Community Watch Corps is a good development for combating crimes in my community	2.77	1.11	Accepted
8.	Community Watch Corps collaborate with military and police in the fight against crime	2.83	1.07	Accepted
9.	Hostilities by host communities disrupt the success of war against banditry	2.69	1.12	Accepted
10.	Community Watch Corps reinforced by military and police	2.77	1.10	Accepted
		2.76	1.09	

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 6 shows that the mean rating ranges from $M = 2.69$, $SD = 1.12$ to $M = 2.83$, $SD = 1.07$ with overall mean of $M = 2.76$, $SD = 1.09$ that is $< M = 2.50$ and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents have accepted that there is strong collaboration between the Community Watch Corps and law enforcement agencies in combating the incidence of banditry in Katsina State.

Research Question Three: What is the level of perception among community members on the role of Community Watch Corps activities in maintaining security?

Table 7: Community members' level of perception on the role of the Community Watch Corps in maintaining security

S/N	Statements	M	SD	Decision
11.	I like the way Community Watch Corps operates security measures in my community	2.80	1.09	Accepted
12.	Community Watch Corps constitute menace in my community	2.74	1.11	Accepted
13.	I have trust on Community Watch Corps' effectiveness in my community	2.74	1.11	Accepted
14.	There have been lots of improvements on security services in my community since the inception of the Community Watch Corps	2.64	1.13	Accepted
15.	I see the Community Watch Corps as being reliable in fighting crimes	2.65	1.10	Accepted
		2.71	1.11	

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 7 revealed that the mean rating ranges from $M = 2.64$, $SD = 1.13$ to $M = 2.80$, $SD = 1.09$ with overall mean of $M = 2.71$, $SD = 1.11$ that is $< M = 2.50$ and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents' opinions do not significantly differ in their mean ratings on their perceptions on the performance of the Community Watch Corps in Katsina State.

Research Question Four: What are the challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities in their efforts to combat banditry?

Table 8: Challenges faced by Community Watch Corps activities in their efforts to combat banditry

Statements	M	SD	Decision
16. There is a lack of synergy between the Community Watch Corps with other security agencies	2.84	1.09	

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17.	There is insufficient funds allocation to Community Watch Corps from the State Government for procurement of safety equipment in times of danger	2.70	1.13
18.	Lack ongoing public relations and enlightenment efforts to increase awareness about the Community Watch Corps' role and activities	2.94	1.07
19.	continuous training and retraining of Community Watch officers	2.96	1.03
20.	Lack of patriotism among some Community Watch officers and security agents to fight against insurgency	2.96	1.01
		2.88	1.07

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The result in the Table 8 shows that the mean rating ranges from $M = 2.70$, $SD = 1.13$ to $M = 2.96$, $SD = 1.03$ with overall mean of $M = 2.88$, $SD = 1.07$ that is $< M = 2.50$ and falls under acceptance region indicating that the individual mean scores are more than the average mean of 2.50. It can be inferred that the respondents have accepted that the Community Watch Corps are faced with challenges in their efforts to combat banditry in Katsina State.

Conclusion

Based on the researches questions answered, the study concluded that Community Watch Corps are active and effective toward eradicating the menace of perennial insecurity such as banditry acts perpetrated by bandits and hooligans aided by unscrupulous informants in Katsina state. Inauguration of Community Watch Police is indeed a segment of fulfilling economic policies aimed at engaging the teeming youths in prolific ventures to avert them from falling preys against evil intrigues of criminal groups.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made

1. The government should revitalize Community Watch Corps to be an effective tool for maintaining stability and safety of the community.
2. Communities should be work in energy with the Community Watch Corps as vigilant in fighting against crimes to enhance safety and stability in the community and social development.
3. The government and security stakeholders should redouble efforts in funding the Community Watch Corps to improve effective community policing and prevention of crimes
4. The Community Watch Corps should be equipped with sophisticated arms, shield, information technology devices and tracking system to combat crime rates in the affected communities.

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